

Quantitative Analysis of Sentiment Expression Across Large Language Models: A Comparative Study Using Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions

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Abstract:

Recent advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) have dramatically transformed the landscape of natural language processing, yet our understanding of how these models express and manipulate emotional content remains limited. This study presents a comprehensive analysis of sentiment expression across multiple prominent LLMs, including Llama 8B, Gemini 1.5 Flash, ChatGPT 4, and Claude 3.5 Sonnet. Using Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions as a theoretical framework, we evaluate how different LLMs express and combine emotional states through generated text. Our analysis employs both LIWC (Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count) and SALLEE (Syntax-Aware Lexical Emotion Engine) to quantify emotional expression across 50 text generations per sentiment per model. Results reveal distinctive patterns in how different LLMs handle emotional intensity and emotional combinations, with significant variations in consistency and accuracy across models. These findings have important implications for both practical applications of LLMs and theoretical understanding of artificial emotional expression.

Terminology, Abbreviations, Links, etc.

- **SA:** Sentiment Analysis
- **LLMs:** Large Language Models
- **LIWC:** Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count
- **SALLEE:** Syntax-Aware Lexical Emotion Engine
- **Emotion:** The expression of feelings through word choice and language patterns, varying in both nature and intensity.
- **Tone:** The specific emotional quality used to address a particular audience or situation, revealed through word choice and phrasing.
- **Voice:** The writer's unique personality and perspective as expressed through their writing, creating a distinctive and recognizable presence.
- **Style:** The technical choices in writing construction, including sentence structure, vocabulary, and literary devices.
- **Mood:** The overall emotional atmosphere created across a text through sustained use of language and literary devices.
- **Sentiment:** The fundamental positive, negative, or neutral attitude expressed in text, which influences how emotional meaning is conveyed throughout.

Introduction

The rapid evolution of Large Language Models has revolutionized natural language processing, enabling increasingly sophisticated text generation across diverse contexts. While substantial research has examined these models' capabilities in tasks ranging from translation to code generation, their handling of emotional content remains relatively unexplored. Understanding how LLMs express and manipulate sentiment is crucial, as these models increasingly mediate human-computer interaction in contexts where emotional resonance is essential.

The current research landscape reveals a significant gap in our understanding of how different LLMs approach sentiment and emotion expression. While extensive literature exists on sentiment analysis of human-generated text, the unique characteristics of LLM-generated content present novel challenges and opportunities for analysis. Sentiment analysis knowledge gathered from human-produced language may not fully capture the nuances of artificially generated emotional expression, particularly when examining how models combine and modulate different emotional states.

Our study addresses this research gap through a systematic comparison of sentiment expression across four major LLMs. We specifically examine how these models handle emotional intensity gradients and emotional combinations, using Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions (1980) as our theoretical framework. This model provides a structured approach to examining

both baseline emotions and more intense versions thereof, allowing us to evaluate whether LLMs' emotional expressions align with theoretically predicted patterns.

Methodology

Our research design combines quantitative analysis with a structured data collection process, ensuring precise coverage of emotional expression across multiple models while maintaining consistency in our evaluation approach.

Model Selection and Configuration

We selected four prominent LLMs representing different approaches to language modeling and different scales of parameter count: Llama 8B (accessed via Ollama), Gemini 1.5 Flash, ChatGPT 4, and Claude 3.5 Sonnet. These models were chosen for their widespread use and varying architectural approaches, providing a broad perspective on current LLM capabilities.

Data Collection Process

Sample Size and Structure

The study examined 17 distinct sentiments across four Large Language Models (LLMs): Llama 8B, Gemini 1.5 Flash, ChatGPT 4, and Claude 3.5 Sonnet. For each sentiment-model combination, we generated 50 unique text samples, resulting in a total dataset of 3,400 text generations (17 sentiments × 4 models × 50 generations).

Procedural Controls

To ensure methodological consistency and minimize potential confounding variables, we implemented several key controls:

1. Conversation Isolation:

- Each text generation was conducted within a new conversation instance
- This approach eliminated potential context carryover between generations
- This also ensured that each generation represented an independent sample

2. Prompt Standardization:

- Identical prompt structure maintained across all generations
- Base prompt: "Generate a piece of text in a tone of [sentiment]"
- Control prompt: "Generate a piece of text in a neutral tone"

3. Quality Assurance:

- Real-time monitoring of response completeness

- Verification of prompt-response alignment
- Automated checks for response validity

4. Error Handling:

- Failed generations automatically flagged
- Regeneration protocol for incomplete or error responses
- Documentation of any anomalies or exceptions

This methodological approach ensured consistent and reliable data collection across all models and sentiments, providing a robust foundation for subsequent analysis. The structured protocol maintained experimental control while allowing for systematic comparison across models and emotional categories.

Prompt Structure

The same prompt was used across each of the 50 generations per sentiment as well as across each of the four LLMs. The structure used was chosen to minimize syntactic variations while maintaining natural emotional expression. For control purposes, we also included a neutral prompt.

Control Prompt:

“Generate a piece of text in a neutral tone.”

We considered altering the syntax of the control prompt to align more with the syntax of the others. However, this would have read “Generate a piece of text in a tone of neutrality.” There are slight connotative differences between “neutral” and “neutrality,” so, ultimately, we decided on the prompt structure above. The connotation of “neutral” comes across as less decisive and more along the lines of an uninvolved, passive bystander. Neutrality, on the other hand comes across as decisively, actively neutral.

Other Sentiment Prompts:

“Generate a piece of text in a tone of [sentiment].”

We used this syntax to maintain consistency across the labels (all nouns such as “sadness” or “trust”) on Plutchik’s Wheel. This way, we could keep the parts of speech the same as they appeared within the wheel.

Emotional Framework

Our analysis employs Plutchik’s Wheel of Emotions (1980) as a comprehensive framework for examining emotional expression. This model organizes emotions into primary dyads (basic emotions at different intensities) and secondary dyads (combinations of primary emotions). We systematically examined both baseline and high-intensity versions of eight primary emotions: **joy/ecstasy, trust/admiration, fear/terror, surprise/amazement, sadness/grief, disgust/loathing, anger/rage, and anticipation/vigilance.**

Analysis Tools and Metrics

Our analysis combines two complementary tools: LIWC-22 and SALLEE (Receptiviti, n.d.; Receptiviti, n.d.). They were manually created by James W. Pennebaker and linguists at Receptiviti.

LIWC-22 provides comprehensive dictionary-based analysis, processing text against over 100 psychological and linguistic categories. LIWC calculates the percentage of words matching various emotional and psychological states, offering quantitative metrics for comparing emotional expression across models. The words processed by LIWC are considered individually, not semantically (Receptivity, n.d.).

SALLEE complements LIWC's dictionary-based approach with syntax-aware emotional mapping, providing deeper insight into contextual sentiment and connotative meaning. This dual-tool approach allows us to capture both explicit emotional content and more subtle aspects of emotional expression (Receptivity, n.d.).

Statistical Analysis Framework

Our statistical analysis employs a multi-layered approach to examining emotional expression patterns. For each emotion category, we calculate standard descriptive statistics across all 50 generations, including mean sentiment values, minimum/maximum sentiment values, and distribution characteristics. Correlation analyses examine how well emotional combinations align with Plutchik's theoretical predictions.

Results

Our analyses reveal distinct patterns in how different LLMs handle emotional expression, with notable variations in both consistency and intensity across models. The results are presented through multiple analytical lenses, examining both individual emotional expressions and emotional combinations.

Individual Emotion Expression

Across all models, we observed consistent ability to generate text that matches requested emotional tones, though with varying degrees of precision. The radar charts comparing maximum, minimum, mean, and median of sentiment values reveal several key patterns:

The average standard deviation across all 17 sentiments within each of the four models were as follows (ordered from least to greatest):

All Sentiments

ChatGPT: 0.07898754718

Claude: 0.08001088876

Llama: 0.08150964225

Gemini: 0.1036983686

Baseline intensity avg SD

Llama: 0.0792692893

ChatGPT: 0.07996232462

Claude: 0.08746930069

Gemini: 0.1146542535

Higher intensity avg SD

ChatGPT: 0.07548794212

Claude: 0.076745498

Llama: 0.08332619974

Gemini: 0.08912438896

Emotional Intensity Scaling

Analysis of emotional combinations revealed varying degrees of alignment with Plutchik's theoretical predictions across models (Plutchik, 1980). Key findings include:

1. Control Comparison:
 - a. Neutral tone generations provided effective baseline measurements
 - b. Models showed varying abilities to maintain true neutrality
 - c. Linguistic complexity remained consistent across emotional and neutral generations
 2. Primary Dyads:
 - a. Notable variations in how models handled opposing emotions
 3. Relative Intensity within Primary Dyads:
 - a. The expected relative intensity vs the actual relative intensity of primary dyad sentiments were also analyzed. Findings comparing the median values can be found below (excluding Neutral, which is unpaired). The word of expected higher intensity is bolded within each set below. Bold formatting is also used to draw attention to occurrences of values being "not as expected."
- Joy / **Ecstasy**
 - ChatGPT: as expected
 - Claude: **not as expected**
 - Gemini: **not as expected**
 - Llama: **not as expected**
 - Trust / **Admiration**
 - ChatGPT: **not as expected**
 - Claude: as expected
 - Gemini: as expected

- Llama: **not as expected**
- Fear / **Terror**
 - ChatGPT: as expected
 - Claude: as expected
 - Gemini: **not as expected**
 - Llama: as expected
- Surprise / **Amazement**
 - ChatGPT: as expected
 - Claude: as expected
 - Gemini: as expected
 - Llama: as expected
- Sadness / **Grief**
 - ChatGPT: as expected
 - Claude: **not as expected**
 - Gemini: **not as expected**
 - Llama: **not as expected**
- Disgust / **Loathing**
 - ChatGPT: **not as expected**
 - Claude: **not as expected**
 - Gemini: **not as expected**
 - Llama: **not as expected**
- Anger / **Rage**
 - ChatGPT: as expected
 - Claude: as expected
 - Gemini: **not as expected**
 - Llama: as expected
- Anticipation / **Vigilance**
 - ChatGPT: **-Vigilance; +Anticipation**
 - Claude: **-Vigilance, +Anticipation**
 - Gemini: **-Vigilance, +Anticipation**
 - Llama: **-Vigilance, +Anticipation**

Of the 8 sets across all four LLMs, only 1 set was found to be as expected. 2/8 sets were found to be not as expected across all four LLMs. 4/8 sets had 3 or more values that were not as expected.

It is perhaps most intriguing to examine the Anticipation / Vigilance set. All four LLMs returned results showcasing Vigilance with a negative sentiment value, while Anticipation had a positive sentiment value. Since Plutchik placed these sentiments in the same primary dyad, it's intriguing that the LLM findings would consistently fall on opposite sides of the connotation spectrum.

Discussion

Model-Specific Patterns and Implications

ChatGPT 4 displayed remarkably balanced emotional expression across both primary (baseline) and primary (higher intensity) dyad rings. The model demonstrated particular strength in maintaining emotional consistency across generations while successfully modulating intensity levels, suggesting more controlled emotional expression. Across the four LLMs examined, it had the lowest average standard deviation within the sentiment scores.

Claude 3.5 Sonnet showed a nuanced handling of sentiment expression. It was consistent in its handling of emotional expression while still offering a bit of variability within each sentiment. Across the four LLMs examined, it had the second-lowest average standard deviation within the sentiment scores.

Llama also showed a nuanced handling of sentiment expression. Like Claude, it demonstrated a consistent handling of emotional expression while offering some variability within each sentiment. Across the four LLMs examined, it had the second-highest average standard deviation within the sentiment scores.

Gemini 1.5 Flash demonstrated the highest variability in emotional expression, both in baseline-intensity sentiments and higher-intensity sentiments. This variability suggests a less constrained approach to emotional expression, potentially offering more creative but less predictable outputs. Across the four LLMs examined, it had the highest average standard deviation within the sentiment scores.

Consistency vs. Expressiveness Trade-offs

Our results highlight an important trade-off between consistency and expressiveness in LLM emotional expression. Models demonstrating higher consistency in emotional expression often showed more limited range in their emotional combinations, while those with greater expressiveness typically displayed more variability in their outputs. This trade-off has important implications for model selection and application design:

1. Application Considerations:

- High-consistency models may be preferred for professional communication
- More expressive models might better serve creative applications
- Hybrid approaches might be necessary for complex applications

2. Development Implications:

- Potential change in how consistency and expressiveness are balanced and/or prioritized
- Potential for context-dependent emotional expression

- Importance of emotional stability in model training

Limitations and Future Directions

While our study provides valuable insights into LLM emotional expression, several limitations and opportunities for future research emerge:

1. Methodological Limitations:

- Reliance on English-language expressions of emotion
- Potential influence of prompt structure on emotional expression
- Limited context for emotional generation

2. Future Research Opportunities:

- Cross-cultural analysis of emotional expression
- Investigation of contextual emotional adaptation
- Long-term stability of emotional expression patterns
- Multi-modal emotional expression analysis
- Further exploration focusing on Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions (1980), potentially examining other rings in the Primary Dyads as well as the Secondary and Tertiary Dyads (our research group has already started on this front).

Lit Review

Literature Review: Sentiment Analysis of LLM-Generated Text

1. Introduction

Sentiment analysis, the computational study of opinions, emotions, and attitudes, is a cornerstone of natural language processing (NLP). Its evolution from simple machine learning models to advanced neural networks and now large language models (LLMs) like GPT-4 has reshaped how sentiment is analyzed and understood. This review examines foundational and contemporary research, focusing on sentiment analysis techniques, datasets, tools like LIWC and SALLEE, and their application to LLM-generated text.

2. Foundations of Sentiment Analysis

2.1. Early Research and Techniques

Bo Pang et al. (2002) pioneered sentiment classification using machine learning techniques, introducing supervised approaches that remain influential. Bing Liu et al. (2004) advanced this with techniques for mining and summarizing customer reviews, emphasizing sentiment extraction from unstructured text. Guang Qiu et al. (2011) contributed to aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) by proposing double propagation for opinion word expansion, paving the way for fine-grained sentiment analysis.

2.2. Comprehensive Surveys

Several surveys provide critical overviews of sentiment analysis techniques:

- Bing Liu (2012, 2015): Reviewed sentiment analysis trends, including opinion mining and domain-specific challenges.
- Zhang et al. (2018): Focused on datasets and future challenges, highlighting the shift toward deep learning methods.
- Kumar et al. (2023): Addressed tasks like ABSA, sentiment classification, and sentiment trend analysis with a focus on transformer models.
- Hua et al. (2024): Conducted a systematic review of ABSA, emphasizing neural networks and domain-specific applications.

2.3. Benchmarks and Datasets

SentiBench by Ribeiro et al. (2015) established benchmarks for evaluating sentiment analysis methods, offering insights into state-of-the-art techniques. These benchmarks continue to be adapted for LLM-generated text.

3. Sentiment Analysis with Large Language Models

3.1. Strengths of LLMs in Sentiment Analysis

Tai et al. (2024) highlighted LLMs' ability to perform large-scale sentiment analysis, particularly in contexts requiring contextual understanding. Their flexibility enables zero-shot and few-shot learning, reducing reliance on annotated datasets.

3.2. Analysis of Sentiment in Media

Rozado et al. (2022) applied transformer-based models to analyze longitudinal sentiment trends in news headlines. Their findings revealed shifts in media tone, showcasing LLMs' ability to capture nuanced sentiment patterns over time.

3.3. Emotional and Moral Sentiments

He et al. (2024) explored how LLMs reflect emotions and moral sentiments embedded in their training data. They found that while LLMs are adept at replicating sentiment, they also inherit biases, necessitating ethical safeguards.

3.4. Challenges in Sentiment Analysis with LLMs

Nguyen-Son et al. (2024) and Antoun et al. (2023) discussed the challenges of detecting and analyzing sentiment in text generated by large models. These include:

- **Overfitting Patterns:** LLM-generated text often exhibits reproducible patterns, complicating sentiment variability.
 - **Scaling Challenges:** Larger LLMs produce text closer to human-like variability, making fine-grained sentiment analysis more complex.
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4. Tools for Sentiment Analysis of LLM-Generated Text

4.1. Receptiviti's LIWC and SALLEE

Receptiviti is a leader in psycholinguistic analysis, offering tools like Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) and Syntax-Aware Lexical Emotion Engine (SALLEE), which were used in this research:

- **LIWC:** A psycholinguistic tool that categorizes words into psychologically meaningful groups, such as pronouns, articles, and emotion-related words (e.g., joy, anger). Its 6,400-word dictionary enables comprehensive analysis of the emotional and psychological undertones in text.
- **SALLEE:** Detects 14 distinct emotions and overall sentiment in text, providing nuanced insights into how emotions are expressed. It assesses present, past, and anticipated emotions, making it especially useful for LLM-generated content.

4.2. VADER and TextBlob

- **VADER:** A lexicon and rule-based sentiment analysis tool designed for short, informal texts. It excels at analyzing sentiment in social media-style content, making it useful for conversational LLM outputs.
- **TextBlob:** A simple Python library for sentiment scoring, allowing for rapid prototyping and analysis of LLM-generated text.

4.3. Transformer-Based Sentiment Models

- **BERT-Based Models:** Pre-trained transformers like BERT and RoBERTa can be fine-tuned for sentiment tasks. These models are highly effective for analyzing nuanced sentiment in complex LLM-generated text (Hoang et al., 2019).

4.4. SentiStrength and SentiWordNet

- **SentiStrength:** Designed for short informal texts, it assigns both positive and negative sentiment scores, useful for social media or casual LLM outputs (Yang, H. et al., 2024).
- **SentiWordNet:** A lexical resource that assigns sentiment polarity scores to WordNet synsets, ideal for domain-specific applications (Baccianella, 2010).

4.5. Cloud-Based APIs

- **AWS Comprehend:** A scalable API for classifying sentiments into positive, negative, neutral, or mixed categories (Amazon, n.d.).
- **Google Cloud Natural Language API:** Offers multilingual sentiment analysis, useful for analyzing LLM outputs in different languages (Google, n.d.).

4.6. CoreNLP and IBM Watson Tone Analyzer

- **CoreNLP:** Uses recursive neural networks for structured sentiment analysis, effective for hierarchical analysis of longer LLM-generated text (Stanford Natural Language Processing Group, n.d.).
- **IBM Watson Tone Analyzer:** Goes beyond sentiment to assess emotional tones and social tendencies, providing insights into conversational LLM-generated text (IBM, n.d.).

5. Ethical and Practical Implications

5.1. Ethical Concerns in Sentiment Analysis

He et al. (2024) highlighted ethical concerns, particularly biases in LLM training data. These biases affect the representation of emotions and opinions, raising questions about transparency and fairness in sentiment analysis.

5.2. Practical Applications

LLM-based sentiment analysis has significant applications in:

- **Media Monitoring:** Tracking sentiment trends in news and social media (Rozado et al., 2022).
- **Customer Feedback Analysis:** Summarizing opinions from reviews (Liu et al., 2024).

- Human-Computer Interaction: Enhancing conversational agents with emotional intelligence (Huang et al., 2024).

5.3. Addressing Biases

Future research must prioritize methods to mitigate biases in sentiment reflection and improve interpretability. He et al. (2024) suggested integrating ethical evaluation frameworks into sentiment analysis systems.

6. Future Research Directions

6.1. Multimodal Sentiment Analysis

Huang et al. (2024) proposed integrating text with visual and auditory data to enhance sentiment detection in multimodal environments, an area that remains underexplored in LLM-generated content.

6.2. Benchmark Development

Ribeiro et al. (2015) advocated for creating benchmarks specifically tailored to LLM-generated text. These benchmarks should incorporate domain-specific sentiment analysis tasks.

6.3. Fine-Tuning for Sentiment Tasks

Zhang et al. (2024) suggested refining LLMs for sentiment-specific tasks by incorporating task-specific datasets, a direction also supported by Kumar et al. (2023).

Conclusion

This study provides comprehensive insight into how different LLMs handle emotional expression, revealing distinct patterns and capabilities across models. Our findings demonstrate that while all examined models can effectively generate emotionally-aligned text, they do so with varying degrees of consistency, intensity, and sophistication in emotional combinations.

The frequent divergence from Plutchik's theoretical predictions suggests the need for revised frameworks for understanding artificial emotional expression.

Future research should focus on developing emotion models more aligned with LLM capabilities and expanding analysis to include secondary and tertiary emotional combinations. This could even be extended to multimodal analyses.

Another potential area of focus is further analysis of Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions, perhaps including secondary dyads, tertiary dyads, and further rings within the primary dyads. This research group is already continuing research within this specific realm.

There are also implications within the wider LLM field. The observed variations in emotional expression patterns suggest different models may be better suited for different applications, from creative writing to professional communication. For example, models with smaller standard deviations within tone are more emotionally consistent — a trait that could be useful in professional writing. More variability generally pairs well with creative efforts.

Furthermore, our results highlight the complex relationship between consistency and expressiveness in LLM emotional expression, suggesting important considerations for both model selection and model training/development.

These findings contribute to both theoretical understanding of artificial emotional expression and practical applications of LLMs. As these models continue to evolve and users find new applications, understanding emotional expression capabilities of LLMs becomes increasingly crucial. Future research building on these findings will be essential for developing more sophisticated and nuanced approaches to artificial emotional expression.

Our work establishes a foundation for systematic comparison of emotional expression across LLMs while highlighting important areas for future investigation. As the field continues to advance, the frameworks and methodologies developed in this study will provide valuable tools for understanding and improving emotional expression in artificial intelligence systems.

Bibliography

1. Amazon. (n.d.). Sentiment. Retrieved from <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/comprehend/latest/dg/how-sentiment.html>
2. Antoun, W. et al. (2024). From Text to Source: Results in Detecting Large Language Model-Generated Content. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/html/2309.13322v2>
3. Antoun, W. et al. (2023) Towards a Robust Detection of Language Model Generated Text: Is ChatGPT that Easy to Detect? Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.05871>
4. Azwarni, N.S. et al. (2024) Evaluating TextBlob, Lexicon, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, and ChatGPT Approaches for Sentiment Analysis of NASDAQ Listed Companies. Retrieved from <http://www.jatit.org/volumes/Vol102No13/20Vol102No13.pdf>
5. Baccianella, S. et al. (2010) SentiWordNet 3.0: An Enhanced Lexical Resource for Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/L10-1531/>

6. Google. (n.d.). Natural Language API Basics. Retrieved from <https://cloud.google.com/natural-language/docs/basics>
7. He, Z., Guo, S., Rao, A., & Lerman, K. (2024). Whose emotions and moral sentiments do language models reflect? Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.11114>
8. Hoang et al. (2019) Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis using BERT. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/W19-6120/>
9. Huang, D.-M., Van Rijn, P., Sucholutsky, I., Marjeh, R., & Jacoby, N. (2024). Characterizing similarities and divergences in conversational tones in humans and LLMs by sampling with people. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/2024.acl-long.565/>
10. Hutto, C. et al. (2014) VADER: A Parsimonious Rule-Based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Text. Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaai.org/index.php/ICWSM/article/view/14550>
11. IBM. (n.d.). Class ToneAnalyzerV3. Retrieved from <https://watson-developer-cloud.github.io/node-sdk/master/classes/toneanalyzerv3.html>
12. Kumar, A. et al. (2023) Causal Effect Regularization: Automated Detection and Removal of Spurious Correlations. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2306.11072>
13. Kumar, A. et al. (2023) Causal Inference Using LLM-Guided Discovery. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2310.15117>
14. Main, Paul. Structural Learning. (n.d.). The emotion wheel - A tool for developing emotional literacy. Retrieved from <https://www.structural-learning.com/post/emotion-wheel>
15. Nguyen-Son, H. Q. et al. (2024) SimLLM: Detecting Sentences Generated by Large Language Models Using Similarity between the generation and its Re-generation. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/2024.emnlp-main.1246/>
16. Pang, B., Lee, L., & Vaithyanathan, S. (2002). Thumbs up? Sentiment classification using machine learning techniques. *Proceedings of the ACL-02 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, 10, 79–86. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/W02-1011/>
17. Pennebaker, J. W. (2011). *The secret life of pronouns: What our words say about us*. Bloomsbury Press.
18. Plutchik, R. (1980). *Emotion: A psychoevolutionary synthesis*. Harper & Row.
19. Receptiviti. (n.d.). *Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC)*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.receptiviti.com/liwc>
20. Receptiviti. (n.d.). *Syntax-Aware Lexical Emotion Engine (SALLEE)*. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://docs.receptiviti.com/frameworks/emotions>
21. Ribeiro, F. N., Araujo, M., Gonçalves, P., Gonçalves, M. A., & Benevenuto, F. (2015). A benchmark comparison of state-of-the-practice sentiment analysis methods. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286302059_A_Benchmark_Comparison_of_State-of-the-Practice_Sentiment_Analysis_Methods
22. Rozado, D., Hughes, R., & Halberstadt, J. (2022). Longitudinal analysis of sentiment and emotion in news media headlines using automated labeling with transformer language models. Retrieved from <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0276367>

23. Sharma, N. A., et al. (2024). A review of sentiment analysis: Tasks, applications, and deep learning techniques. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s41060-024-00594-x>
24. Stanford Natural Language Processing Group. (n.d.) CoreNLP. Retrieved from <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/>
25. Tai, R. H., Bentley, L. R., Xia, X., Sitt, J. M., Fankhauser, S. C., Chicas-Mosier, A. M., & Monteith, B. G. (2024). An examination of the use of large language models to aid analysis of textual data. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378178132_An_Examination_of_the_Use_of_Large_Language_Models_to_Aid_Analysis_of_Textual_Data
26. WhyLabs (2024). 7 Ways to Evaluate and Monitor LLMs. Retrieved from <https://whylabs.ai/blog/posts/7-ways-to-evaluate-and-monitor-llms>
27. Yang, H. et al. (2024). Large Language Models Meet Text-Centric Multimodal Sentiment Analysis: A Survey. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/html/2406.08068v2>
28. Zhang, W. et al. (2024) Sentiment Analysis in the Era of Large Language Models: A Reality Check. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/2024.findings-naacl.246.pdf>

Reference Photos

<https://www.structural-learning.com/post/emotion-wheel>

<https://www.betterup.com/blog/emotion-wheel>

Data Visualizations

Radar Charts

For each radar chart, color-coding is as follows:

- Highest sentiment value (green)
- Mean sentiment value (yellow)
- Median sentiment value (orange)
- Lowest sentiment value (red)

ChatGPT - Tone Ranges Radar Chart

Claude - Tone Ranges Radar Chart

Gemini - Tone Ranges Radar Chart

Llama - Tone Ranges Radar Chart

													Actual SD	"Expected" SD (given numbers of surrounding sentiments)
NEUTRAL - CHATGPT	NEUTRAL - CHATGPT - MAX	0.3895216401	NEUTRAL - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.04081632653	NEUTRAL - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.1671154425	NEUTRAL - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.1596594334	NEUTRAL - CHATGPT - SD	0.09918616813				
ECSTASY - CHATGPT	ECSTASY - CHATGPT - MAX	0.5487270078	ECSTASY - CHATGPT - MIN	0.2160793039	ECSTASY - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.3939018274	ECSTASY - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.3911573393	ECSTASY - CHATGPT - SD	0.06547781742	0.06547781742			
JOY - CHATGPT	JOY - CHATGPT - MAX	0.5056179775	JOY - CHATGPT - MIN	0.2102145584	JOY - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.3827470804	JOY - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.3813391947	JOY - CHATGPT - SD	0.06847880502			0.06847880502	
ADMIRATION - CHATGPT	ADMIRATION - CHATGPT - MAX	0.3942054434	ADMIRATION - CHATGPT - MIN	0.1105958729	ADMIRATION - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.2862106491	ADMIRATION - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.2835126664	ADMIRATION - CHATGPT - SD	0.06189840173	0.06189840173			
TRUST - CHATGPT	TRUST - CHATGPT - MAX	0.4208333333	TRUST - CHATGPT - MIN	0.1926605505	TRUST - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.3237887431	TRUST - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.3342695265	TRUST - CHATGPT - SD	0.05791440688			0.05791440688	
TERROR - CHATGPT	TERROR - CHATGPT - MAX	-0.1315699072	TERROR - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.4314344034	TERROR - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.2984597263	TERROR - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.2935451212	TERROR - CHATGPT - SD	0.0629843178	0.0629843178			
FEAR - CHATGPT	FEAR - CHATGPT - MAX	-0.05494505495	FEAR - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.2961165049	FEAR - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.172120518	FEAR - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.1756336681	FEAR - CHATGPT - SD	0.06196498307			0.06196498307	
AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT	AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT - MAX	0.4957770832	AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT - MIN	0.04361054767	AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.3069854411	AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.3105459951	AMAZEMENT - CHATGPT - SD	0.07434897815	0.07434897815			
SURPRISE - CHATGPT	SURPRISE - CHATGPT - MAX	0.2689129053	SURPRISE - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.07591153616	SURPRISE - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.08056319829	SURPRISE - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.0688709732	SURPRISE - CHATGPT - SD	0.07401011149			0.07401011149	
GRIEF - CHATGPT	GRIEF - CHATGPT - MAX	0.02958579882	GRIEF - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.2888888889	GRIEF - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.1479546058	GRIEF - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.1552374635	GRIEF - CHATGPT - SD	0.07103608945	0.07103608945			
SADNESS - CHATGPT	SADNESS - CHATGPT - MAX	0.1717791411	SADNESS - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.2385321101	SADNESS - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.04324342775	SADNESS - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.04399414052	SADNESS - CHATGPT - SD	0.07875286756			0.07875286756	
LOATHING - CHATGPT	LOATHING - CHATGPT - MAX	-0.1348314607	LOATHING - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.4600732878	LOATHING - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.2920598644	LOATHING - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.2888991673	LOATHING - CHATGPT - SD	0.07457046241	0.07457046241			
DISGUST - CHATGPT	DISGUST - CHATGPT - MAX	-0.1914893617	DISGUST - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.5344158643	DISGUST - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.3698973281	DISGUST - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.3684307978	DISGUST - CHATGPT - SD	0.07978256046			0.07978256046	
RAGE - CHATGPT	RAGE - CHATGPT - MAX	-0.05653117197	RAGE - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.4956803793	RAGE - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.2699588798	RAGE - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.2732756652	RAGE - CHATGPT - SD	0.1087127865	0.1087127865			
ANGER - CHATGPT	ANGER - CHATGPT - MAX	0.06313723613	ANGER - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.4089954123	ANGER - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.1944649882	ANGER - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.1980358109	ANGER - CHATGPT - SD	0.08986418757			0.08986418757	
VIGILANCE - CHATGPT	VIGILANCE - CHATGPT - MAX	0.1488673139	VIGILANCE - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.2025316456	VIGILANCE - CHATGPT - MEAN	-0.02578550834	VIGILANCE - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	-0.02613821282	VIGILANCE - CHATGPT - SD	0.08487468349	0.08487468349			
ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT	ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT - MAX	0.3471502591	ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT - MIN	-0.09803921569	ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT - MEAN	0.1075814896	ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT - MEDIAN	0.07301886792	ANTICIPATION - CHATGPT - SD	0.1289306749			0.1289306749	
									MEAN	0.07898754718	0.07548794212		0.07996232462	

											Actual SD	"Expected" SD (given numbers of surrounding sentiments)
NEUTRAL - CLAUDE	NEUTRAL - CLAUDE - MAX	0.1333333333	NEUTRAL - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.1216216216	NEUTRAL - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.02185082554	NEUTRAL - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.01985811392	NEUTRAL - CLAUDE - SD	0.04646671945		
ECSTASY - CLAUDE	ECSTASY - CLAUDE - MAX	0.5431727586	ECSTASY - CLAUDE - MIN	0.252743077	ECSTASY - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.4124115895	ECSTASY - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.409514202	ECSTASY - CLAUDE - SD	0.06033317451	0.06033317451	
JOY - CLAUDE	JOY - CLAUDE - MAX	0.5470521334	JOY - CLAUDE - MIN	0.201754386	JOY - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.4208660106	JOY - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.4185696904	JOY - CLAUDE - SD	0.06841256384		0.06841256384
ADMIRATION - CLAUDE	ADMIRATION - CLAUDE - MAX	0.5003791765	ADMIRATION - CLAUDE - MIN	0.006944444444	ADMIRATION - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.2659507521	ADMIRATION - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.2657911494	ADMIRATION - CLAUDE - SD	0.08784545389	0.08784545389	
TRUST - CLAUDE	TRUST - CLAUDE - MAX	0.4371257485	TRUST - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.00598802395	TRUST - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.2589762821	TRUST - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.2590194511	TRUST - CLAUDE - SD	0.080998795		0.080998795
TERROR - CLAUDE	TERROR - CLAUDE - MAX	-0.01891586674	TERROR - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.2728285767	TERROR - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.1554846464	TERROR - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.1608391608	TERROR - CLAUDE - SD	0.06283800834	0.06283800834	
FEAR - CLAUDE	FEAR - CLAUDE - MAX	0.07940161105	FEAR - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.2912172573	FEAR - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.1294341415	FEAR - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.1301741294	FEAR - CLAUDE - SD	0.0758777971		0.0758777971
AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE	AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE - MAX	0.4497521051	AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE - MIN	0.1786688812	AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.3039163867	AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.3048646812	AMAZEMENT - CLAUDE - SD	0.04886031858	0.04886031858	
SURPRISE - CLAUDE	SURPRISE - CLAUDE - MAX	0.2977255996	SURPRISE - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.08283233133	SURPRISE - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.08196583879	SURPRISE - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.07283190491	SURPRISE - CLAUDE - SD	0.07487992474		0.07487992474
GRIEF - CLAUDE	GRIEF - CLAUDE - MAX	0.1337579618	GRIEF - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.2249853716	GRIEF - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.01176409132	GRIEF - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.01422385077	GRIEF - CLAUDE - SD	0.08674620322	0.08674620322	
SADNESS - CLAUDE	SADNESS - CLAUDE - MAX	0.175	SADNESS - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.3011664899	SADNESS - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.05928814173	SADNESS - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.06383616384	SADNESS - CLAUDE - SD	0.1201497725		0.1201497725
LOATHING - CLAUDE	LOATHING - CLAUDE - MAX	-0.08955223881	LOATHING - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.4459546926	LOATHING - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.2915674587	LOATHING - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.2955819934	LOATHING - CLAUDE - SD	0.06922870189	0.06922870189	
DISGUST - CLAUDE	DISGUST - CLAUDE - MAX	-0.3115942029	DISGUST - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.5776397516	DISGUST - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.4261103441	DISGUST - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.4237456255	DISGUST - CLAUDE - SD	0.06639887391		0.06639887391
RAGE - CLAUDE	RAGE - CLAUDE - MAX	-0.02091254753	RAGE - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.5199728415	RAGE - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.2278319577	RAGE - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.1897905857	RAGE - CLAUDE - SD	0.1360295745	0.1360295745	
ANGER - CLAUDE	ANGER - CLAUDE - MAX	0.01987476178	ANGER - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.4860360531	ANGER - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.1934260033	ANGER - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.1630869999	ANGER - CLAUDE - SD	0.1201461623		0.1201461623
VIGILANCE - CLAUDE	VIGILANCE - CLAUDE - MAX	0.1090909091	VIGILANCE - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.1646341463	VIGILANCE - CLAUDE - MEAN	-0.0270138824	VIGILANCE - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	-0.02583148559	VIGILANCE - CLAUDE - SD	0.06208254908	0.06208254908	
ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE	ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE - MAX	0.2445520581	ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE - MIN	-0.2209302326	ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE - MEAN	0.04978676622	ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE - MEDIAN	0.0533428165	ANTICIPATION - CLAUDE - SD	0.0928905161		0.0928905161
									MEAN	0.08001088876	0.076745498	0.08746930069

											Actual SD	"Expected" SD (given numbers of surrounding sentiments)
NEUTRAL - GEMINI	NEUTRAL - GEMINI - MAX	0.35	NEUTRAL - GEMINI - MIN	-0.4347826087	NEUTRAL - GEMINI - MEAN	0.03400797587	NEUTRAL - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.04880952381	NEUTRAL - GEMINI - SD	0.1326431264		
ECSTASY - GEMINI	ECSTASY - GEMINI - MAX	0.5518429727	ECSTASY - GEMINI - MIN	0.155351062	ECSTASY - GEMINI - MEAN	0.3727586344	ECSTASY - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.37239623	ECSTASY - GEMINI - SD	0.08293851487	0.08293851487	
JOY - GEMINI	JOY - GEMINI - MAX	0.636342974	JOY - GEMINI - MIN	0.2496770026	JOY - GEMINI - MEAN	0.4637505178	JOY - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.4826776023	JOY - GEMINI - SD	0.09439190386		0.09439190386
ADMIRATION - GEMINI	ADMIRATION - GEMINI - MAX	0.4788743686	ADMIRATION - GEMINI - MIN	-0.001979218209	ADMIRATION - GEMINI - MEAN	0.286897195	ADMIRATION - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.284045375	ADMIRATION - GEMINI - SD	0.1041882054	0.1041882054	
TRUST - GEMINI	TRUST - GEMINI - MAX	0.4666666667	TRUST - GEMINI - MIN	0.05555555556	TRUST - GEMINI - MEAN	0.2134776555	TRUST - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.1792857143	TRUST - GEMINI - SD	0.1198681558		0.1198681558
TERROR - GEMINI	TERROR - GEMINI - MAX	-0.03076923077	TERROR - GEMINI - MIN	-0.2888731229	TERROR - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.1536760895	TERROR - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.1378063942	TERROR - GEMINI - SD	0.06784832319	0.06784832319	
FEAR - GEMINI	FEAR - GEMINI - MAX	0.01075268817	FEAR - GEMINI - MIN	-0.3920972644	FEAR - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.2094763104	FEAR - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.2124910597	FEAR - GEMINI - SD	0.09202069679		0.09202069679
AMAZEMENT - GEMINI	AMAZEMENT - GEMINI - MAX	0.5389424781	AMAZEMENT - GEMINI - MIN	-0.1745644429	AMAZEMENT - GEMINI - MEAN	0.2770178551	AMAZEMENT - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.2723416024	AMAZEMENT - GEMINI - SD	0.1106615949	0.1106615949	
SURPRISE - GEMINI	SURPRISE - GEMINI - MAX	0.2511520737	SURPRISE - GEMINI - MIN	-0.09438414346	SURPRISE - GEMINI - MEAN	0.08557585161	SURPRISE - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.128540305	SURPRISE - GEMINI - SD	0.0935484945		0.0935484945
GRIEF - GEMINI	GRIEF - GEMINI - MAX	0.1553871142	GRIEF - GEMINI - MIN	-0.1764705882	GRIEF - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.02654312948	GRIEF - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.02002224694	GRIEF - GEMINI - SD	0.07744671965	0.07744671965	
SADNESS - GEMINI	SADNESS - GEMINI - MAX	0.1111111111	SADNESS - GEMINI - MIN	-0.3274336283	SADNESS - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.1444364982	SADNESS - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.1590555267	SADNESS - GEMINI - SD	0.09119920233		0.09119920233
LOATHING - GEMINI	LOATHING - GEMINI - MAX	-0.02831050228	LOATHING - GEMINI - MIN	-0.4105858776	LOATHING - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.222287352	LOATHING - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.2095686383	LOATHING - GEMINI - SD	0.09187650468	0.09187650468	
DISGUST - GEMINI	DISGUST - GEMINI - MAX	-0.00542931831	DISGUST - GEMINI - MIN	-0.7461775548	DISGUST - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.4558345571	DISGUST - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.4995348804	DISGUST - GEMINI - SD	0.1558128621		0.1558128621
RAGE - GEMINI	RAGE - GEMINI - MAX	-0.09472419579	RAGE - GEMINI - MIN	-0.4809709779	RAGE - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.2844646246	RAGE - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.2716803141	RAGE - GEMINI - SD	0.09189780794	0.09189780794	
ANGER - GEMINI	ANGER - GEMINI - MAX	-0.09148679741	ANGER - GEMINI - MIN	-0.2903075489	ANGER - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.2931904046	ANGER - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.2918846114	ANGER - GEMINI - SD	0.1447941849		0.1447941849
VIGILANCE - GEMINI	VIGILANCE - GEMINI - MAX	0.03947368421	VIGILANCE - GEMINI - MIN	-0.2972972973	VIGILANCE - GEMINI - MEAN	-0.08425176491	VIGILANCE - GEMINI - MEDIAN	-0.08257713249	VIGILANCE - GEMINI - SD	0.08613744102	0.08613744102	
ANTICIPATION - GEMINI	ANTICIPATION - GEMINI - MAX	0.3982647635	ANTICIPATION - GEMINI - MIN	-0.09756097561	ANTICIPATION - GEMINI - MEAN	0.1837090109	ANTICIPATION - GEMINI - MEDIAN	0.2160537482	ANTICIPATION - GEMINI - SD	0.1255985277		0.1255985277
									MEAN	0.1036983686	0.08912438896	0.1146542535

										Actual SD	"Expected" SD (given numbers of surrounding sentiments)		
NEUTRAL - LLAMA	NEUTRAL - LLAMA - MAX	0.3372093023	NEUTRAL - LLAMA - MIN	-0.1	NEUTRAL - LLAMA - MEAN	0.04328366303	NEUTRAL - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.03681431354	NEUTRAL - LLAMA - SD	0.08490000594			
ECSTASY - LLAMA	ECSTASY - LLAMA - MAX	0.5445344855	ECSTASY - LLAMA - MIN	0.124507688	ECSTASY - LLAMA - MEAN	0.3075420977	ECSTASY - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.3158671252	ECSTASY - LLAMA - SD	0.08733428336	0.08733428336		
JOY - LLAMA	JOY - LLAMA - MAX	0.5616400866	JOY - LLAMA - MIN	0.2933031326	JOY - LLAMA - MEAN	0.4176574531	JOY - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.4124508121	JOY - LLAMA - SD	0.06536724523	0.06536724523		
ADMIRATION - LLAMA	ADMIRATION - LLAMA - MAX	0.4040039383	ADMIRATION - LLAMA - MIN	0.07865168539	ADMIRATION - LLAMA - MEAN	0.2358757907	ADMIRATION - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.2237291087	ADMIRATION - LLAMA - SD	0.07958197709	0.07958197709		
TRUST - LLAMA	TRUST - LLAMA - MAX	0.4160583942	TRUST - LLAMA - MIN	0.004576659039	TRUST - LLAMA - MEAN	0.2625093647	TRUST - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.2842227009	TRUST - LLAMA - SD	0.09966121046	0.09966121046		
TERROR - LLAMA	TERROR - LLAMA - MAX	-0.07376872894	TERROR - LLAMA - MIN	-0.3253909889	TERROR - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.1987373619	TERROR - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.1966639368	TERROR - LLAMA - SD	0.06693828996	0.06693828996		
FEAR - LLAMA	FEAR - LLAMA - MAX	-0.05494505495	FEAR - LLAMA - MIN	-0.2921561197	FEAR - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.1681145152	FEAR - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.1696017762	FEAR - LLAMA - SD	0.05868356314	0.05868356314		
AMAZEMENT - LLAMA	AMAZEMENT - LLAMA - MAX	0.4044526013	AMAZEMENT - LLAMA - MIN	-0.04003594249	AMAZEMENT - LLAMA - MEAN	0.1605494791	AMAZEMENT - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.1610156133	AMAZEMENT - LLAMA - SD	0.0889667262	0.0889667262		
SURPRISE - LLAMA	SURPRISE - LLAMA - MAX	0.4103857356	SURPRISE - LLAMA - MIN	-0.1090550844	SURPRISE - LLAMA - MEAN	0.1206067064	SURPRISE - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.1197362705	SURPRISE - LLAMA - SD	0.09922730581	0.09922730581		
GRIEF - LLAMA	GRIEF - LLAMA - MAX	0.1349036403	GRIEF - LLAMA - MIN	-0.2834277272	GRIEF - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.06859617534	GRIEF - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.06824023951	GRIEF - LLAMA - SD	0.08223661095	0.08223661095		
SADNESS - LLAMA	SADNESS - LLAMA - MAX	0.09830508475	SADNESS - LLAMA - MIN	-0.2349862945	SADNESS - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.08288155572	SADNESS - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.08278829287	SADNESS - LLAMA - SD	0.08022100546	0.08022100546		
LOATHING - LLAMA	LOATHING - LLAMA - MAX	0.09826046074	LOATHING - LLAMA - MIN	-0.3873146279	LOATHING - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.2279007241	LOATHING - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.2418150002	LOATHING - LLAMA - SD	0.1071093281	0.1071093281		
DISGUST - LLAMA	DISGUST - LLAMA - MAX	-0.03056768559	DISGUST - LLAMA - MIN	-0.3853390827	DISGUST - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.2469848201	DISGUST - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.2569914054	DISGUST - LLAMA - SD	0.07541547611	0.07541547611		
RAGE - LLAMA	RAGE - LLAMA - MAX	-0.00216644379	RAGE - LLAMA - MIN	-0.3785689314	RAGE - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.1912984032	RAGE - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.1915854413	RAGE - LLAMA - SD	0.08270214037	0.08270214037		
ANGER - LLAMA	ANGER - LLAMA - MAX	-0.04364694471	ANGER - LLAMA - MIN	-0.3346806646	ANGER - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.1774824316	ANGER - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.1578696372	ANGER - LLAMA - SD	0.07167327693	0.07167327693		
VIGILANCE - LLAMA	VIGILANCE - LLAMA - MAX	0.138576779	VIGILANCE - LLAMA - MIN	-0.1757501531	VIGILANCE - LLAMA - MEAN	-0.06484205631	VIGILANCE - LLAMA - MEDIAN	-0.07477147291	VIGILANCE - LLAMA - SD	0.0717402419	0.0717402419		
ANTICIPATION - LLAMA	ANTICIPATION - LLAMA - MAX	0.3077733513	ANTICIPATION - LLAMA - MIN	0.004114735524	ANTICIPATION - LLAMA - MEAN	0.1557486562	ANTICIPATION - LLAMA - MEDIAN	0.1588046161	ANTICIPATION - LLAMA - SD	0.08390523124	0.08390523124		
										MEAN	0.08150964225	0.08332619974	0.0792692893